

MS27 Code repository for standard Dataselect-WS from new non-standard big datasets in seismology

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable presents the repository of reference including different services and tools to provide new seismological data types in standard formats.

An analysis of the challenges related to the inclusion of big datasets in seismological data centers, regarding data formats and services was published in a high-impact-factor journal (Seismological Research Letters). On this manuscript, we present initial conclusions from the user survey mentioned earlier and summarize the landscape in seismology regarding big datasets and what this implies for standard services and data formats in the community. Potential solutions are also discussed.

Other outcomes from the Task 6.7 are also presented in this report. For instance, a User Survey answered by seismologists working with big datasets.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
DAS	Distributed acoustic sensing. Technology by which as fiber-optic cable is used as a seismological sensor.
Dataselect-WS	The Dataselect web service is the international standard web service defined by the FDSN for data provisioning service. This should be run at every seismological data centre.
FDSN	The International Federation of Seismographic Networks is the organization in which discussions and decisions about standards for the seismological community are being held. This includes data formats, specifications of data and metadata services, management of network codes to identify datasets, among other topics.

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Executive summary

- An introduction to the main aims of this Task is presented.
- We present a brief summary of a publication in a high-impact-factor journal with some of the outcomes of this Task, which have been carried out by GEOFON (Germany) in collaboration with two other data centers, RESIF from France and IRIS from USA (Quinteros et al, 2021, doi: [10.1785/0220200390](https://doi.org/10.1785/0220200390)).
- We developed in the context of this task the software *dastools*, a set of tools to work and standardize new data types in our community. The *dastools* repository is openly available and is described briefly here. *dastools* has been published with doi: [10.5880/GFZ.2.4.2021.001](https://doi.org/10.5880/GFZ.2.4.2021.001)

1 Introduction

Within the seismological community, the last decades have been characterised by large amount of new additional permanent and temporary conventional seismic stations becoming available. It is already clear that there are some game-changing technologies under development. The demand for new dense observations using new technologies is advancing fast. This includes Large N deployments consisting of huge numbers of easy-to-install geophones; cheap sensors (e.g. MEMs accelerometers) used by mobile devices as well as for infrastructure monitoring; and fibre-optic based technologies, that are each starting to show their great potential in providing quality data with a wide spectrum of applications ranging from Tsunami early warning to Infrastructure monitoring. Although data quality and resolution of the three groups mentioned above are different, for seismic monitoring and archival infrastructures, these groups have in common the potential to produce large volumes of data in a very short period of time due to both the extremely dense spatial and temporal resolutions.

- Large N deployments are becoming popular thanks to the availability of cost/power effective instruments. Typically of short duration, they may imply a very varying number of sensors (from a few tens to thousands), and are presently carried out with high frequency sensors. Some manufacturers have only high frequency sampling. Field installations are easy, and are often carried out by teams of non-specialist personnel.
- Cheap sensors are already used since about a decade in educational projects showing capabilities to provide satisfactory recordings for earthquakes. Recently, a number of crowdsourcing projects have been launched making available a growing number of additional sensors from private users to the seismological community. These crowd-sourced projects include tailor-made cheap sensors and digitizers for private consumers as well as usage of existing sensors in mobile devices. In both cases the easiness to access new data, sometimes in area where conventional seismic stations are not available, is making these data valuable for real-time applications in the context of rapid response and earthquake early warning.
- Fibre-optic can be used as seismic arrays measuring ground motion from earthquakes using the so called distributed acoustic sensing technique (DAS) with existing underground fibre-optic cables (normally used for telecommunications, such as internet, television, and telephone service) up to tens of kilometres long or deploying dedicated short fibre-optic cables. Alternative usage of fibre-optic communication cables can be also achieved by placing conventional sensors along their repeaters (typically 50-100 km intervals) and only use the fibre-optic for communication, for example at the ocean floor using existing submarine cables. The former allows for example to image the internal structure of faults with high resolution as well as to infer creeping processes of faults at sub-micrometre step (Jousset et al., 2018). The latter has the potential to provide an unparalleled global network of real-time data for ocean climate and sea level monitoring and disaster mitigation from earthquake and tsunami hazards (Howe, 2016).

This considerable increase in the data generation is very challenging for all seismological data centres hosting data, because there is no clear idea how this could be managed by our standard web services, which are very stable and mature, but have never faced the need to support an on-the-fly conversion of a big volume of data from proprietary to standard formats.

Several Large-N experiments have been already carried out in seismology and archived at some FDSN data centres using the actual standards. Data from these experiments are currently distributed via standard FDSN services but with some limitations due to the fast-growing number of experiments as well as additional DAS data expected to be produced in the near future.

2 State-of-the-art at global level

One of the main outcomes of this task, that is expected to be a blueprint for the community, was the publication in a high-impact-factor journal (SRL) of a paper presenting the challenges for the community regarding these new data types (Quinteros et al., 2021). In this section, we briefly summarize what has been published in the article. More details can be found in the publication.

Large-N deployments and the new DAS systems can generate tens to hundreds of terabytes of data at a small fraction of the cost of using traditional seismometers and geophones for equivalent data volumes. As the price of collecting data becomes drastically cheaper, a corresponding and dramatic increase in the volume of data being collected provides a potential scientific bonanza. However, storing these data in perpetuity is a significant and daunting challenge, as is delivering datasets exceeding a few tens of terabytes. High-performance/ high-throughput computational resources (HPC/HTC) are increasingly necessary to process these data and these resources are not typically provided by the repositories, nor are they co-located with the repositories.

GEOFON (Germany), RESIF (France) and IRIS (USA), three of the most important seismological data centers at the global level, carried out this analysis of the new challenges imposed by this drastic change in data generation, and attempted to identify the needs of the community and to look for common solutions and best practices for managing very large data sets while maintaining their traditional data services.

2.1 User Survey

A survey was conducted of selected and self-identified large data users. We classified them in three different categories of data volume: small (1-9 TB), medium (10-50 TB), and large (50+ TB). Some selected results from the survey can be observed in Figure 1.

Both medium and large data users anticipated a use of a variety of data formats, but primarily the miniSEED standard and some with HDF5 (PH5 and ASDF). However, for users planning to work with 20+ TB, the option of miniSEED reduces considerably in comparison to HDF5-based formats or other less standard formats. A generic HDF5-based solution could have some advantages not only for data centers but also for users needing to process their large datasets in an HPC-friendly format. The main disadvantage for data centers is that HDF5 formatted data cannot currently be streamed on the fly as they are read by the data provisioning systems (Fig. 1, data format).

The medium data users primarily declared their intention to work with classical broadband seismic data, some Large-N nodal data and a bit of DAS, while large data users indicated mostly DAS, with some nodal and broadband seismic (Fig. 1, data type).

Many medium and large users indicated that they would like to transfer data to their own computer infrastructure or their institutional infrastructure. Many also indicated a preference to deliver data to an HPC center, but just one anticipated relying on commercial cloud

providers. Among users working with 20+ TB there seems to be a clear trend in favour of paying for the computational resources for data processing (some dependent on grant allowance). The common challenge for many is efficient access to large volume data, either due to access interface issues or limited transfer capability.

An unexpected result is that as the size of the datasets grows, users are more conservative with the hosting of their data and refuse to take alternatives like cloud hosting. Two reasons for this are the high cost of this type of storage, and also the uncertainty and lack of control of the data management. Amazon-like cloud system solutions, which since years has been a hot topic, is considered only by a few users as an option, and only in the case of datasets of less than 20 TB (Fig. 1, data staging).

Fig.1 - Different aspects of users' data workflows by size of datasets to be requested. Counts at the base of bars are the number of respondents. Smaller datasets tend to be requested in miniSEED format, but HDF5-based formats are preferred for larger datasets. Requests to get nodal experiment data will generate medium size datasets, while users plan to get very large datasets from DAS

experiments. Python is the preferred programming independent of the dataset size. Small datasets are expected to be staged in the user infrastructure, while larger datasets in some HPC facility. Only a few users mentioned their will to stage data in a cloud service (after Quinteros et al., 2021).

2.2 Data archival

If data centers are expected to increase their archive sizes by at least one order of magnitude (or even more), it might not be feasible to keep all of the data online (Figure 2). Offline storage should probably be considered inside the data center or provided by external services. This will raise the storage capacity but data would have to be staged on demand, and with limited size and retention time.

Fig. 2 - Evolution of the data archived yearly at each data center (red, black, and blue curves). The error bars on the right show the expected size range of a single dataset for a Large-N (yellow) and a DAS (green) experiment. It can be seen that a single large dataset could be equivalent in size to a whole year of the typical datasets currently being archived (after Quinteros et al., 2021).

2.3 Metadata

There exist comprehensive metadata standards in seismology that are well suited for large nodal data sets or other classical seismic data sets. However, newer, emerging data types such as DAS are not as well handled by these standards where the concepts of a network, station, location and a channel are different and the fundamental instrument responses are new. Therefore, one of the most difficult tasks for data centers attempting to identify and implement standard services is to standardize DAS metadata through the definition of new metadata schemas. StationXML, the international standard for seismic metadata, is not a good fit with the technical features of DAS interrogators and the generated datasets. There is a need to tackle this in a smart way in order to make these data available and interoperable with all popular tools used within the community, which expect typical seismic waveforms with some minimum set of requirements on their metadata, and the possibility of mixing different data types.

2.4 Data provision

Currently, the FDSN-standard suite of web services (fdsnws-station and fdsnws-datasselect) are used by many researchers to discover and download data. Approximately 90% of the fdsnws-datasselect requests received delivered less than 5 MB of data. The miniSEED format along with the fdsnws-datasselect webservice are well designed for this purpose. However, users may make many small requests to optimize their data retrieval success and assemble the complete dataset that they desire on their computers. The size of the datasets needed by the community is probably larger than observed in our statistics. It is still unclear what the download pattern for Large-N or DAS data would be, but downloads of entire datasets are expected.

The distribution of large data sets (50+ TB) is challenging due to bandwidth constraints. As mentioned previously, one of the main results of the survey we conducted was that *the full resolution data is not needed for most studies*, particularly for DAS. Instead, a set of products derived from the original data would satisfy most users. The derived data products are often a significantly reduced volume making them more feasible for archiving and distribution by existing data centers and systems. While the derivative products are useful in reducing the burden of transferring bulky data, the need to transfer large volumes is not eliminated for all users.

Another significant challenge is the lack of available services to handle the transmission of large volumes. The current data transfer standard in global broadband seismology (fdsnws-datasselect), defines a synchronous web service interface that accepts arbitrary data selections and is expected to begin returning data with little or no delay. It has become a highly successful mechanism, but although allowed, requesting large data volumes with this service has the risk of causing connection timeouts. It is difficult to efficiently resume transfers following broken connections, which are increasingly likely with very large volumes.

Also, maintaining acceptable performance can require significant software and system engineering by the data centers.

2.5 Data processing

The user's need to process data in a remote environment (e.g. cloud computing, containers), means that other factors should also be considered by data centers. For instance, even if a data center can provide a container or Jupyter notebook with direct processing of the data, solutions need to be developed to limit restricted dataset access to authorized users. A similar issue is related to the data organization (format and structure). The data center can expose (or let the user access) what exists in the storage system so the user will in principle be able to use only the storage format available. It will be difficult (impossible in some cases) to stage a new dataset in another format to be accessed by the user. Therefore, the internal data format and organization needs to be known by the user. As each data center is free to organize the data in whatever way is optimal to them, data processing software cannot easily be used across different data center computational facilities.

The transparent federation of data is probably the biggest challenge for data centers because it includes not only all the improvements and developments mentioned in this article, but also the edge case in which multiple large datasets are requested from different data centers. In such a case, even running the code on top of the data is not a solution. That would only save the transfer from that data center, but there is still the problem of requesting all the other data. Some public initiatives exist in the United States and Europe to propose solutions to the problem of federated data (e.g. XSEDE/Jetstream and the European Open Science Cloud). However, there are still no solutions available that cover all the aspects mentioned above.

2.6 Outcome

Despite present initiatives trying to tackle the problem of big seismological datasets and how they can be archived, delivered, and processed, data centers are facing a situation similar to that from the mid-80's. Namely, the amount of data generated was much bigger than the data centers could safely and sustainably archive. At that moment, the temporary solution was to keep only time windows of interest (e.g. waveforms related to an earthquake) and discard the rest of the data after some time. What has been learned from this experience is that discarding data is not the best option to consider, as illustrated by present day research in data mining, new types of seismic signals, and imaging techniques using seismic noise (all data NOT related to an earthquake).

At present, the IRIS, GEOFON and RESIF data centers recognize that it is not possible for them to permanently archive very large datasets such as DAS due to prohibitive costs of long-term archiving. Safe storage (involving multiple copies) of such large datasets available online is presently not possible either. Therefore, the seismological data centers should explore a strategy for delivering datasets through automatic asynchronous services to designated destinations such as computing facilities where data pre-processing or

processing could occur. For very large datasets, a common strategy is needed for storing only standard data products such as spatially and/or temporally down-sampled data, and/or small windows of highly sampled data.

3 Description of the repository

dastools (Quinteros, 2021, [3]) is a software package developed within Task 6.7 and including a set of tools to work with data generated by DAS systems. As explained previously, the main problem of these type of data is not only the generation of large volume datasets, but its lack of standardization.

The *dastools* package provides a library to access and manage TDMS datasets generated by DAS systems. This consists of Python classes which are the core of the tools provided. These classes can be imported by the users in their own code and include in it all the flexibility of *dastools*.

3.1 Data conversion

dasconv is a tool which lets you convert and manipulate seismic waveforms in TDMS format and export them into the standard miniSEED. In addition to that, as the DAS data is acquired at a high sampling rate, the conversion can optionally include a decimation of the data in order to create some of the derived products mentioned in the previous section. These products are feasible to be archived and opened to users as any other standard seismological dataset.

Data acquired from experiments with DAS systems are usually stored in one folder. Files within this folder have names indicating the experiment and the start time of the waveforms saved. An example of the files generated in a test experiment is shown below.

```
$ ls -l
total 1577352
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:38 default.UTC_20190508_093735.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:38 default.UTC_20190508_093805.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:39 default.UTC_20190508_093835.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:39 default.UTC_20190508_093905.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:40 default.UTC_20190508_093935.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:40 default.UTC_20190508_094005.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:41 default.UTC_20190508_094035.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:41 default.UTC_20190508_094105.409.tdms
-rwxrwxrwx 1 user staff 49965056 May  8 09:42 default.UTC_20190508_094135.409.tdms
```

There, 'default' is the name of the experiment and the rest is the start time with the following format:

```
experiment_TZ_YYYYMMDD_HHmms.fff.tdms
```

dasconv provides also a *TDMS* class which needs to receive one mandatory parameter to be instantiated, which is actually the experiment name and how all file names in the containing

folder start with. A detailed explanation on how to use it on your own programs can be found in the documentation available in the repository.

3.1.1 Examples

Export waveforms from channels 800, 802 and 804 starting at 2019-05-08T09:37:35.409000 until 2019-05-08T09:38:05.400000.

The waveforms will be exported to miniSEED format after being decimated by a factor of 5 (e.g. from 1000Hz to 200Hz).

```
dasconv -d /home/user/test/ --start "2019-05-08T09:37:35.409000" --end  
"2019-05-08T09:38:05.400000" default --chstart 800 --chstop 805 --  
chstep 2
```

Export waveforms from channels 0 and 1 from the beginning of the measurements until 2019-05-08T09:32:15.

The waveforms will be exported to miniSEED format after being decimated by a factor of 5 (e.g. from 1000Hz to 200Hz).

```
dasconv -d /home/user/test/ --endtime "2019-05-08T09:32:15" default --  
chstart 0 --chstop 1
```

Export waveforms from channels 0 to 4 from the beginning of the measurements until 2019-05-08T09:32:15.

The waveforms will be exported to miniSEED format after being decimated by a factor of 5 (e.g. from 1000Hz to 200Hz).

```
dasconv -d /home/user/test/ --endtime "2019-05-08T09:32:15" default --  
chstart 0 --chstop 4 --decimate 5
```

3.2 Data provision

tdmsws is a stand-alone implementation of the FDSN Dataselct web service, which is able to serve miniSEED data extracted from a folder with TDMS files.

A typical help message from *tdmsws* looks like the following:

```
% tdmsws -h  
usage: tdmsws [-h] [-mc] [-l {DEBUG,WARNING,INFO,DEBUG}]  
tdmsws is an FDSN Dataselct implementation to read TDMS files  
optional arguments:  
-h, --help            show this help message and exit  
-mc, --minimalconfig  Generate a minimal configuration file.
```

```
-l {DEBUG,WARNING,INFO,DEBUG}, --log {DEBUG,WARNING,INFO,DEBUG}
    Increase the verbosity level.
```

The "mc" switch creates a config file, which should be placed in the same folder as the TDMS files. The file includes all needed options and configuration variables which will be read by the software before being able to serve the data.

The user is expected to edit this file and provide the basic information about the DAS experiment before running the service. One can see below a typical config file.

```
[General]
experiment = default
loglevel = INFO

[NSLC]
network = XX
location =
channel = FH1
```

The "experiment" variable refers to the first part of the filenames in the folder. For instance, in the example above, all files will start with "default" and then a timestamp including the timezone (or UTC) will follow (see example in the Data conversion section above).

The variables "network", "location" and "channel" will be fixed to define the N.S.L.C code. Only the station will vary and it will always be a number referring to the stream number for the experiment. From the example above, the only valid code would be "XX.00001..FH1", "XX.00002..FH1", ..., "XX.00123..FH1" up to all available streams.

3.2.1 Running the service

To run the service you should "cd" into the folder with the TDMS files and make sure that there is a file called "tdmsws.cfg" with its variables properly configured. Then, you can simply call the program, which will start and run as a daemon. The service will listen to all requests in port 7000.

3.2.2 Web service methods

The methods supported by the web service here provided are:

- **query**: The six required parameters "net", "sta", "loc", "cha", "start", and "end" are supported including their aliases. Errors are returned as specified in the standard.
- **version**: returns the version number in text/plain format.

- **application.wadl**: returns details about implemented and supported options and parameters.

All these methods are described in the global standard specification provided by the FDSN (see References).

3.3 Data quality check

The evaluation on file corruptions, data gaps and data completeness is performed within the *dasconv* tool, as well as the *tdmsws* service, in order to check for data loss from production to archiving.

We checked that the signal content of the selected chunks of data is preserved while selecting in time, assembling, down-sampling and saving the data. We show in Figure 3 that both the original (raw) and down-sampled signal match through all the spectra range.

Figure 3. Spectra of the DAS raw (1000Hz, blue line) and miniSEED decimated signal (200Hz, red line) for one hour of data from a single channel.

4 Conclusions and future work

We continue our international collaboration with data centers in order to find agreements, which could tentatively become standards. In the context of this task, another outcome that had to be postponed due to the covid situation, was the acceptance of a session chaired by the Task coordinator in the European Seismological Conference, which was supposed to be held in Corfu, Greece, on September 2020. The conference was postponed by one year and the topics of the session are exactly the ones of this task.

We expect to find broader agreements from the discussion in such international forums and groups. Ideally, in the long term, international standards and products should be developed within the framework of the FDSN. The Plenary Meeting will be held on July 2021 and we expect to present and discuss some of these topics.

The package *dastools* will evolve with new functionality and our participation in the forums discussing how metadata should be defined for DAS experiments will be the input needed to enhance its functionality as soon as the discussions come to an agreement. Also, the definition by the community of the derived products from the DAS experiments will be included in the *dasconv* utility to support data center operators in producing standard products.

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